

AGROTOURISM MARKETING STRATEGY: EFFECTIVE INTERNET COMMUNICATIONS

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Keywords.

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Annotation.

The work considers agritourism as a promising, effective and profitable type of tourism. However, at present, agritourism is unpopular among the population choosing other, more expensive types of recreation. The author emphasizes that advertising and promotion of agricultural services in Uzbekistan are underdeveloped and require a new, improved approach to promotion and popularization. In the work, the features were identified and the differences between promotion of services and promotion of goods were formulated. A comparative table of problems and shortcomings of existing means of promoting tourism services was compiled. The authors also developed the structure of the marketing complex of the e-mail service. The article describes the features of effective marketing communications in the field of agritourism. The algorithm of the process of promoting an agritourism product on the Internet is described.

In modern conditions, rural tourism is gaining rapid popularity, thereby occupying a strong position in the tourist services market. As the experience of European countries shows, this type of tourism is one of the most promising types of tourism, due to its positive impact on the development of territories and high income. For example, every third tourist choosing a vacation in France uses the services of rural tourism, in the UK (10%) and Germany (4%) entrepreneurs offer tourist services in rural areas [6].

In the Uzbek market, agritourism services are still gaining popularity, despite the high prospects, thereby there is a need to promote and popularize this type of tourism.

Several global trends contribute to the development of the market and marketing in the field of agritourism, such as: the deterioration of the ecological situation in the world and related problems, the popularization of a healthy lifestyle, the oversaturation of the market with traditional types of tourism, the formation of agritourism for rural residents as the main type of life, development and globalization the Internet, thanks to which farmers and agricultural producers were able to independently sell and promote their services using modern Internet technologies.

An agritourism product is a complex combination of a material product and an intangible service, the features of which are intangibility, impossibility of storage, dependence on seasonal fluctuations, and the mismatch in time between the fact of the sale of tourist services and its consumption. An argotour product is understood not only for its material and intangible characteristics, but also for its development, planning, decision-making regarding the agricultural product range.

Today, tourist trips related to ecological tourism are gaining rapid popularity. Examples of such trips are outdoor recreation, ecological trails, routes in specially protected areas, excursions with environmental education, recreation in the countryside, etc.

As a rule, such routes do not have a long duration, so many can afford to go on an ecological trip for the weekend and temporarily move away from the bustle of the city.

The formation of demand for agritourism is carried out under the influence of the following main factors:

- 1) psychological (popularization of healthy lifestyle: the opportunity to join a healthy lifestyle and spend time interestingly away from the bustle of the city);
- 2) economic (decrease in the population's ability to pay: the organization of an agricultural tour is much more profitable than tours in standard hotel conditions).

The main factors hindering the development of marketing in agritourism in Uzbekistan:

- low communication interaction between Uzbek and foreign tour operators in the provision of agrotourism services in the Uzbek market;
- low competitiveness of Uzbek agrotourism services in the international market according to the criteria of matching the price and quality of services, which in turn limits the target market of tourist enterprises to the framework of the domestic tourist market.

Most of the cultural, natural and recreational resources are used by market entities ineffectively due to the lack of full-fledged information and analytical support for the concept development, promotion and provision of agritourism services. In addition, the participants of the tourism market are required to form an effective system of material incentives for the formation of agritourism business, as well as competent and effective marketing concepts for agritourism services [1].

Thus, in order to implement successful agritourism projects, it is necessary to use marketing research, which are the key mediators of active demand in the tourism market. The successful promotion of agricultural services in the tourist market is based on an effective complex of marketing research.

In general, the promotion of tourist services to the market is significantly different from the promotion of goods. This is due to the intangible nature of the service. Accordingly, the development of a marketing strategy for services is much more difficult in comparison with goods, since the quality of a service can be assessed only after, or at the stage of its consumption, while a product can be assessed before purchase [2].

The process of promotion in the service sector includes not only promotion elements, but also a marketing mix ("7P"), which in total are marketing communications that provide the client with information for making a final decision.

The study of the market for agritourism services is explained by the fact that agritourism is an innovative product that requires detailed marketing research and evaluation.

Currently, income from agritourism in Europe is about 20-30% of the total income of the tourism industry. In Uzbekistan, according to *Uzbektourism*, the income from rural tourism in the total amount is only 2% [5].

Thus, conducting research with an analysis of the sources of resource potential and strategies for the effective use of promotion tools for the development of tourism in rural areas of Uzbekistan is very relevant.

The aim of the study is to identify effective components of marketing activities in the development and promotion of an agritourism product, as well as the use of Internet promotion as an effective method to popularize agritourism services.

Abroad, agritourism is a popular type of recreation, but in Uzbekistan it is not yet sufficiently advertised. Any promotion is useful for popularizing rural recreation, but it should be noted that before choosing methods of promoting tourist services, it is necessary to analyze what problems you may encounter.

Below is a table compiled by the authors, based on electronic resources [3, 4]:

Comparative table of the problems of methods of promoting tourism services

Promotional means in tourism	Problems
Newspapers magazines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - not all printed editions are published often, as a rule, most magazines publish one issue per month, thus a rare advertising message may be ineffective; - many newspapers and magazines, if they publish advertising, then it contains various topics, therefore, it is necessary to provide a bright and unusual advertising offer so that it does not get lost among other offers; - advertisements in magazines are of higher quality, but this also creates additional inconveniences, because the production and preparation of such advertisements can take much longer (sometimes up to several months) than for a newspaper. During this time, significant changes can occur, both in the advertiser itself and in the market for advertised goods or services.
Radio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - lack of visual impact on potential consumers; - advertising messages on the radio are short and it is not always possible to convey to consumers all the important information; - many listeners turn on the radio "for the background", listen to music in the car, or, for example, during the working day, and when it comes time for advertising, the message may well be missed.
A television	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the high cost of making a commercial and launching it on the air; - for many viewers, the advertising message is an "irritant", as it interrupts the viewing of a favorite movie and TV show; - impossibility to cover all segments of the population with TV advertising.
Outdoor advertising	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - advertising messages should be short so that a person can read it in 2-3 seconds. Ninety-five percent of the time, either the message or the audience is in motion; - the creation of a banner is a rather long process, therefore, the promotion of a short-term advertising campaign is excluded, including it will be quite expensive; - the massiveness of this type of advertising and great competition

Internet promotion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - some netizens are biased towards any type of advertising on the Internet. For example, too intense viral advertising, constant mailing of messages with intrusive texts and advertising offers can make a negative impression on a potential client and damage the company's image; - an advertising message on the Internet can be harmed by mistrust and a considerable number of fraudsters on the Internet; - it is not always possible to reach a wider part of the audience of potential consumers, for example, young people and middle-aged people spend most of their time on the Internet than older people.
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As you can see from the table, each of the means of promotion has its own problems. But, if we stop at Internet promotion, then it should be noted that this tool is more mobile and adaptable to the external environment.

Internet promotion on the agritourism services market is one of the marketing elements and has its own distinctive features from traditional promotion:

- The most complete provision of information about the advertised object;
- The ability to create a dialogue with a potential consumer by various means;
- Ability to focus direct impact on the target audience and a specific consumer.

The Uzbek Internet audience is more characterized by positive development dynamics and quantitative growth. Taking into account this trend, the advertiser on the agro-tourism services market should focus on potential consumers who increase the intensity of using the Internet and, therefore, are more likely to respond to the company's offer [1].

Thus, we can highlight the main advantages of online advertising:

- alternative offer - Internet advertising, as a rule, is the least intrusive, thereby reducing the risk of negative perception of advertising by a potential consumer, which cannot be said, for example, about TV advertising;
- setting target targets - allows you to select the target audience from the entire available audience, and select the necessary methods, resources and technologies in order to show advertising to it (thematic sites, forums, search engines, etc.);
- interactivity - the implementation of interaction between a person and the media, i.e. the consumer independently chooses the channels for receiving advertising information;
- high efficiency - is a quick response to all customer requests. Helps to effectively solve all newly arisen questions and problems in the current time.

The following algorithm is proposed for the process of promoting agritourism services on the Internet:

1. Creation of an Internet portal to promote agricultural services in the tourism market.
2. Publication of informational articles about agritourism, allowing the most interesting and detailed story about this type of tourism, listing its advantages, disadvantages, problems and opportunities in order to interest not only tourists, but also entrepreneurs and sponsors.
3. Search engine optimization of the site.
4. Use of contextual, banner, display advertising services on the Internet, by connecting advertising tools;
5. Promotion of services using social networks.
6. Reputation management in the Internet space. It is necessary to track the appearance

of information about the company, products, services, and eliminate the negative. This can be accomplished by organizing reviews, forums, etc.

Search engine optimization and promotion of a tourist portal is an effective tool for marketing communications to provide a potential consumer with access to information about agricultural services. When developing a strategy for promoting a tourist portal, it is necessary to remember about the peculiarities of the tourism business: the seasonality of demand / supply and a relatively low profitability.

When analyzing the effectiveness of the site, it is necessary to monitor the number of visitors, the number of conversions achieved (conversion is the ratio of the number of site visitors who completed the target action to the total number of site visitors or any target audience), transactions and income from a specific client. However, some key data will remain unavailable. They are associated with the level of satisfaction of visitors, which is especially important in cases where content marketing is used as the main means of sales promotion [6].

The most informative indicators of website performance, in our opinion, include:

- site traffic (number of unique views, number of returned);
- the time spent by a potential consumer on the site;
- the number of viewed pages, thanks to which you can understand the product preferences of visitors and how they interact with the site;
- the dynamics of visiting new and old site visitors.

By analyzing the above indicators, you can determine the most productive site pages that establish the most effective communication contact with a potential consumer. Also, the analysis of these indicators determines the effectiveness of website promotion:

- popularity and "promotion" of the page - the ratio of the number of unique visitors in the previous period and in the current one;
- "session time" - the time (one visit) spent by a potential consumer on the agritourism website;
- "bounce statistics" - analysis of the effectiveness of the sections of the site, for example, if a user opened one page of the site and left it without activating other requests, then the information on the site did not attract a potential consumer [1].

In conclusion, it should be noted that when developing the concept of an agritourism product, an effective promotion strategy is needed, which would help create a competitive tourist facility that attracts and satisfies the needs of both domestic and foreign tourists.

With the help of Internet marketing technologies, the company can attract the necessary segment of consumers, thereby increasing the volume of sales and the level of popularity of agricultural services. The use of online promotion in the marketing strategy of a tourism product will help the company to remain competitive in the face of rapid changes in the tourism market.

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